

REVIEW ARTICLE

**THERAPEUTIC APPROACHES TO STIFF PERSON SYNDROME:
FROM IMMUNOMODULATION TO TARGETED THERAPY**

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Abstract:

Stiff Person Syndrome (SPS) is a rare, chronic neurological disorder characterized by progressive muscle stiffness and painful spasms, often associated with autoantibodies against glutamic acid decarboxylase (GAD). Although the exact pathogenesis remains incompletely understood, growing evidence points to autoimmune mechanisms playing a central role. Traditional treatments have focused on symptom management through muscle relaxants and benzodiazepines. However, recent advances in immunomodulatory therapies, including intravenous immunoglobulin (IVIG), plasmapheresis, corticosteroids, and rituximab, have offered more targeted strategies to address the underlying autoimmune dysfunction. Emerging therapies such as monoclonal antibodies, stem cell-based approaches, and antigen-specific immunotherapies are under investigation and may provide more durable disease control. This review summarizes current therapeutic options, evaluates their efficacy and safety profiles, and explores future directions in the treatment of SPS. The aim is to provide clinicians and researchers with a comprehensive overview of existing and emerging strategies to improve patient outcomes and quality of life.

Keywords: Gamma-Aminobutyric Acid (GABA), GAD Antibodies (Glutamic Acid Decarboxylase), Autoimmune, Neurological, Autoantibodies.

Introduction:

Stiff-person syndrome (SPS) was initially identified in 1956 by Moersch and Woltman following their analysis of 14 patients over a 27-year period. This exceptionally rare neuroimmunologic condition is marked by gradually increasing muscle stiffness and rigidity, often accompanied by painful spasms affecting the muscles of the trunk. Stiff-person syndrome (SPS) is also associated with autoimmune disorders such as type 1 diabetes mellitus, thyroiditis, and pernicious anaemia. ^[1]

Stiff-person syndrome (SPS) is an autoimmune neurological condition caused by disrupted inhibitory GABAergic neurotransmission, primarily linked to the presence of high levels of antibodies against glutamic acid decarboxylase (GAD)—the enzyme responsible for synthesizing the inhibitory neurotransmitter gamma-aminobutyric acid (GABA). Approximately 5–10% of people with SPS also exhibit symptoms such as cerebellar ataxia, epilepsy, or nystagmus. These cases fall under the broader category of GAD-antibody spectrum disorders (GAD-SD), which also includes autoimmune epilepsy, cerebellar ataxia, limbic encephalitis, and myoclonus. SPS-SD represents a treatable subset of autoimmune neurological diseases characterized by GAD antibody–related neuronal hyperexcitability. Among these, SPS is the most frequently occurring and poses significant clinical challenges due to its gradual onset and complex symptom profile, often leading to delayed diagnosis and intervention. This is particularly critical given that SPS is a progressively worsening disorder with a distinctive pathophysiology, marked by impaired reciprocal inhibitory GABAergic signaling and autoimmunity, necessitating early and sustained therapeutic strategies. Additionally, the autoimmune attack on inhibitory neurotransmission in SPS-SD is often intensified by other synaptic autoantibodies, such as those targeting the glycine- α 1 receptor, amphiphysin, and gephyrin—especially in cases of paraneoplastic SPS. [2]

Types of Stiff Person Syndrome (SPS):

1. Classic SPS

Classic stiff-person syndrome (SPS) typically begins subtly, with symptoms gradually worsening over several months. The condition often first presents as rigidity and stiffness in the trunk, particularly in the thoracolumbar area, caused by persistent contraction of the abdominal and paraspinal muscles. Patients often report difficulty with movements such as bending or turning and commonly describe their gait as resembling that of a “tin man.” As the disease progresses, this muscle rigidity extends to the proximal muscles of the upper and lower limbs. [3]

Over time, the condition can cause various chronic orthopedic complications, including exaggerated lumbar lordosis, joint deformities, and abnormal body posture, often giving patients a “statue-like” appearance. These physical changes are frequently accompanied by gait abnormalities and repeated falls. Additionally, individuals may experience painful, widespread muscle spasms and heightened startle reactions triggered by sudden tactile, visual, or auditory stimuli, as well as intense emotions. Psychological symptoms are also common, with many patients developing depression, task-specific phobias, fear of open spaces, and anticipatory anxiety related to the occurrence of spasms and exaggerated startle responses. [5]

Because of the frequent presence of psychiatric comorbidities, stiff-person syndrome (SPS) is often misdiagnosed as a functional neurological disorder or a primary psychiatric illness. Symptoms tend to fluctuate throughout the day and typically worsen with physical or emotional stress, cold temperatures, or infections. In the early stages, distal and facial muscles are generally unaffected. The intensity and duration of painful muscle spasms can vary significantly; in some instances, these spasms may persist for hours—a condition known as “status spasticus”—which may necessitate emergency medical care and intravenous muscle relaxants. In rare cases, the respiratory muscles may also become involved. [6]

2. Partial SPS Variants

Stiff limb syndrome is characterized by localized spasms in one limb, with minimal or no involvement of the trunk muscles. The abnormal posturing seen in the affected distal limb can mimic dystonia. Although muscle stiffness may eventually spread, it remains most pronounced in the initially affected limb. In contrast, stiff trunk syndrome involves spasms limited to the axial muscles, with the limbs remaining unaffected. In rare cases, patients may exhibit eye movement abnormalities such as oscillopsia, opsoclonus, or nystagmus. The cerebellar variant of SPS (SPS-Cer) is characterized by symptoms including dysmetria, gait ataxia, and nystagmus, alongside the core feature of muscle stiffness. [7]

3. Paraneoplastic SPS

Some researchers have also reported cases of paraneoplastic SPS tends to present with more pronounced stiffness in the neck and upper limbs. These patients often exhibit a more rapid therapeutic response and marked clinical improvement following the treatment or removal of the underlying malignancy. [8]

4. Progressive Encephalomyelitis with Rigidity and Myoclonus

Progressive encephalomyelitis with rigidity and myoclonus (PERM) is a more severe form of SPS, marked by a relapsing-remitting course and broader involvement of the central nervous system, particularly the brainstem. This widespread CNS involvement can lead to impaired consciousness or cognitive changes, dysfunction of the extraocular muscles, ataxia, and signs of autonomic failure. [5]

Pathophysiology:

The precise pathogenic role of autoantibodies in stiff-person syndrome (SPS) remains uncertain. All known SPS-related autoantigens are synaptic proteins that play a role in inhibitory synaptic transmission. Presynaptic targets include glutamic acid decarboxylase (GAD) and amphiphysin, while postsynaptic targets involve the GABA(A) receptor-associated protein and gephyrin. [11]

It is believed that SPS autoantibodies exert their effects through pharmacological interference with these targets, rather than causing structural damage to GABAergic neurons. This is supported by the absence of neurological abnormalities beyond increased muscle tone and the observed symptom relief with immunotherapy. Additionally, the fact that most postmortem examinations reveal no significant abnormalities further supports this hypothesis. In some instances, non-specific neuronal and interneuronal loss in the spinal cord has been reported. Notably, a condition referred to as "stiff horse syndrome" has been described, presenting with a stiff gait and muscle tenderness upon palpation. Clinical, electromyographic, and serological findings in these cases closely resembled those seen in SPS. [9] [10]

GAD autoantibodies:

Approximately 60–80% of patients with stiff-person syndrome (SPS) have autoantibodies directed against glutamic acid decarboxylase (GAD), a key cytoplasmic enzyme that regulates the production of gamma-aminobutyric acid (GABA), the brain and spinal cord's primary inhibitory neurotransmitter. GAD is predominantly produced in presynaptic GABAergic neurons of the central nervous system, as well as in pancreatic β -cells within the islets of Langerhans. The precise mechanism by which the immune system targets intracellular GAD remains unclear.

There are two isoforms of GAD—GAD65 and GAD67—but GAD65 is the primary antigenic target in both SPS and type 1 diabetes mellitus (DM). In SPS, GAD autoantibodies bind to both linear and conformational epitopes of the enzyme, whereas in type 1 DM, the antibodies recognize only conformational epitopes. Epitopes are distinct regions of an antigen that the immune system identifies and targets. Linear epitopes are made up of a continuous sequence of amino acids, whereas conformational epitopes are formed from amino acids that are not sequential but come together in a specific three-dimensional structure.

In type 1 DM, GAD autoantibodies typically target the carboxy-terminal or central regions of the enzyme, whereas in SPS, they predominantly bind to the amino-terminal region. This difference in epitope recognition is also evident in T cell responses: T cells from individuals with DM respond to carboxy-terminal epitopes, while those from SPS patients react to amino-terminal epitopes.

The immunoglobulin profile of GAD autoantibodies also differs between the two conditions. In DM, the antibodies are mostly of the IgG1 subtype, while in SPS, the antibody response is broader, including IgG4 and IgM. These distinctions may be disease-specific or could reflect the significantly higher antibody titers seen in SPS—up to 50 times above normal, compared to a tenfold increase typically observed in DM. Though, not all patients with SPS exhibit elevated levels of GAD antibodies.

Notably, the concentration of GAD antibodies in the serum or cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) does not reflect the severity of the disease. As a result, regular monitoring of antibody titers is not required. GAD autoantibodies are not exclusive to SPS or DM and have also been detected in other neurological conditions, such as cerebellar ataxia, myoclonus, epilepsy, and others. The diversity of clinical presentations is believed to stem from differences in epitope recognition by the immune system. ^{[11][12]}

Symptoms of SPS include:

- Muscle stiffness and rigidity primarily affecting the trunk
- Difficulty with movements such as bending and turning
- Stiffness extending to the arms and legs
- Unusual hunched posture
- Stiff, unsteady gait and challenges with walking
- Painful and involuntary muscle spasms
- Frequent falls
- Heightened startle reflex triggered by sounds, visual stimuli, or emotional stress

Individuals with SPS frequently experience psychological symptoms due to the anticipation of spasms and the resulting physical and social limitations. These may include:

- Depression
- Anxiety
- Agoraphobia (fear of open spaces)
- Task-related phobias triggered by activities that may provoke spasms

In the later stages of the condition, the facial muscles may also be affected. Some patients may also suffer from prolonged, intense spasms that necessitate treatment with intravenous muscle relaxants. In rare instances, SPS can impair the respiratory muscles as well. ^[13]

Diagnosis:

A healthcare professional diagnoses stiff person syndrome (SPS) by identifying characteristic signs and symptoms through a combination of examinations and diagnostic tests. During a physical and neurological exam, they will ask detailed questions about your symptoms and medical history.

If SPS is suspected, your provider may recommend several tests, including:

- **Antibody blood test:** This test detects the presence of antibodies against GAD (or other associated antibodies) and helps identify or exclude other possible conditions.
- **Electromyography (EMG):** EMG assesses the electrical activity of muscles and can aid in distinguishing SPS from other neuromuscular disorders.
- **Lumbar puncture (spinal tap):** In this procedure, spinal fluid is collected using a needle inserted into the spinal canal. The fluid is tested for GAD antibodies and other markers to help confirm the diagnosis or rule out alternative conditions.

Diagnosing stiff person syndrome can be challenging due to its rarity and the overlap of symptoms with other disorders, such as ankylosing spondylitis, multiple sclerosis, and various autoimmune diseases.^[14]

Treatment of SPS:**A. GABA-Enhancing Drugs**

These treatments are considered first-line therapies because they enhance GABAergic inhibitory neurotransmission, reduce cortical hyperexcitability, or increase central nervous system GABA levels, thereby positively affecting impaired reciprocal inhibition and alleviating the four core symptoms of SPS described earlier. Their effectiveness as initial therapy has been clearly demonstrated, particularly in a large cohort of male veterans. However, no controlled clinical trials have been conducted or are expected to be conducted with these medications.

B. Immunotherapies

These treatments should be initiated promptly if first-line GABA-enhancing therapies do not provide adequate symptom relief. Delaying the start of immunotherapy is not recommended, as it may lead to irreversible clinical damage or further disease progression, as demonstrated by longitudinal follow-up studies.^[15]

GABA -Enhancing drugs**Benzodiazepines**

Benzodiazepines enhance GABA-mediated pathways, providing both anticonvulsant and anxiolytic effects. They also serve as powerful muscle relaxants and have been a cornerstone in the treatment of stiff-person syndrome (SPS) for many years. Medications like diazepam are commonly preferred for managing SPS symptoms. However, over time, patients often require higher doses to achieve symptom control, which can lead to significant side effects. While some patients can tolerate and need very large doses, any dose increase should be done gradually. Typically, additional or alternative therapies are introduced to minimize adverse effects.^[16]

Clonazepam, at doses ranging from 0.5 to 5 mg, is equally effective as diazepam and may be preferred in some cases. Other benzodiazepines such as alprazolam, lorazepam, and temazepam are also

utilized. Diazepam is particularly effective in managing status spasticus and is best administered intravenously during severe, prolonged spasms, or via the rectal route when needed. ^[15]

Baclofen

Baclofen, which acts as a GABA-B receptor agonist, is frequently used in combination with benzodiazepines to treat spasticity. It was first suggested as a treatment option for stiff-person syndrome (SPS) around two decades ago. Most patients are treated with oral baclofen, although higher doses may sometimes be necessary, which can lead to significant cognitive side effects. Because of its limited penetration into the cerebrospinal fluid (CSF), intrathecal baclofen is often used in cases of severe spasticity. This method has shown substantial benefit in improving symptoms of both classic SPS and its more severe form, progressive encephalomyelitis with rigidity and myoclonus (PERM). ^[17]

Intrathecal baclofen is usually recommended for patients who need high doses of benzodiazepines but cannot tolerate their side effects. However, healthcare providers must exercise caution with intrathecal baclofen, as any disruption in its delivery can cause a severe withdrawal syndrome and potentially fatal autonomic failure. ^[18]

Antiepileptics That Enhance GABA Synthesis or Facilitate GABAergic Transmission

Gabapentin is commonly used in our patients, as it promotes GABA synthesis and helps alleviate painful spasms. Treatment typically begins at 300 mg three times daily, with the dose gradually increased based on patient tolerance. Other GABA-enhancing antiepileptic drugs that may be beneficial—provided they are well tolerated—include vigabatrin, which inhibits GABA transaminase; tiagabine, a GABA reuptake inhibitor; and levetiracetam, which enhances GABAergic transmission. Although pregabalin shares a structural resemblance to GABA, it does not bind to GABA receptors; instead, it targets voltage-gated calcium channels. While it may help with pain, it is generally less effective for spasms and is therefore less favored. ^[19]

Other Antimuscle Spasm Agents: Methocarbamol (Robaxin), Cyclobenzaprine (Flexeril), Dantrolene, and Botulinum Toxin

Methocarbamol (Robaxin), administered at a dose of 1,000 mg four times daily, can be effective in relieving painful spasms and may also be given intramuscularly. Cyclobenzaprine (Flexeril) at 10 mg three times daily has been used in some cases, though it is generally avoided in our practice due to its potential to paradoxically worsen symptoms.

Botulinum toxin can provide substantial relief for individuals with focal SPS. It may be considered for individuals experiencing isolated or regionally painful spasms in accessible areas—such as one leg in stiff-leg syndrome, the face in stiff-face syndrome, or specific muscle groups like the paracervical or lumbosacral paraspinals—particularly when these spasms persist despite other treatments. Though its effects are usually limited to the treated area and are temporary.

Dantrolene, primarily used for malignant hyperthermia, works by binding to ryanodine receptors and reducing intracellular calcium levels through inhibition of calcium release from the sarcoplasmic reticulum. While it may decrease muscle stiffness, its use in SPS is rare.

Overall, the preferred initial antispasmodic treatment includes oral baclofen in combination with gabapentin and low-dose diazepam. The additional agents mentioned above may serve as suitable alternatives if they are well tolerated.

Disease Modifying Immunomodulation/Immunosuppression:

Intravenous Immunoglobulin

Intravenous immunoglobulin (IVIG) is considered the most effective second-line treatment for patients with severe or treatment-resistant stiff-person syndrome (SPS). Initial support for its use came from multiple case reports showing notable improvements in muscle stiffness, exaggerated startle responses, functional ability, and clinical examination findings. Many of these reports also documented radiological and serological improvements. Since then, IVIG has been shown to enhance quality of life in individuals with SPS and to relieve symptoms in patients with the GAD-antibody-positive stiff limb variant.

Although IVIG is generally safe, clinicians should be aware of its potential adverse effects. These may include infusion-related reactions, which can range from mild to severe, and in rare cases, life-threatening anaphylaxis—particularly in individuals with IgA deficiency, for whom IVIG is relatively contraindicated. Other possible side effects include skin rashes, headaches, aseptic meningitis, and renal tubular acidosis. Additionally, IVIG increases the risk of venous thromboembolism, especially in patients with reduced mobility. Arterial thrombosis may also occur, potentially resulting in stroke, myocardial infarction, pulmonary embolism, or ischemia in other organs.

The European Federation of Neurological Societies advises the use of IVIG for SPS patients who show inadequate response to diazepam and/or baclofen and experience significant disability—such as requiring a cane or walker because of severe trunk stiffness and frequent falls. ^[20] ^[16]

Plasmapheresis

While IVIG is generally considered safe, it carries a higher risk of adverse reactions compared to plasmapheresis—particularly in individuals with IgA deficiency, in whom it is contraindicated due to the potential for severe reactions. In contrast, plasmapheresis has shown encouraging outcomes in approximately 56% of patients in a study approved by the Johns Hopkins Hospital (JHH), particularly in cases where first-line treatments were ineffective. Research indicates that plasmapheresis is usually well tolerated, with adverse effects reported in only about 4.75% of recipients. ^[21]

However, the evidence supporting plasmapheresis in SPS is less robust than that for IVIG, and study outcomes have been mixed. The use of plasma exchange in SPS dates back more than two decades. While some case reports have documented improvements in symptoms as well as in serological and electrophysiological markers, other reports have shown no benefit. Patients who responded positively were often also receiving other effective medications concurrently.

The American Society for Apheresis has assigned plasmapheresis a Grade 2C, Category III recommendation for the treatment of SPS, based on a recent case series involving 344 patients in which it was used as an adjunct therapy. The limited recommendation reflects the partial and inconsistent benefit observed, with only about half of the patients showing improvement.

Rituximab

Rituximab, a monoclonal antibody targeting the B-lymphocyte surface antigen cluster of differentiation (CD), has been explored as an effective treatment option for managing SPS. [22]

Rituximab is typically administered in two doses of 350–375 mg/m² spaced 7 to 14 days apart, or as four weekly infusions. This regimen has been associated with significant reductions in symptom severity. In cases where benzodiazepines and monthly IVIG have failed, notable improvement in gait and the ability to walk with minimal assistance has been observed following two doses of rituximab at 500 mg/m², given two weeks apart.

For patients who experience a relapse and test positive for anti-GAD antibodies in serum or cerebrospinal fluid, additional doses administered 6 to 8 months later have shown favorable outcomes. Although there are only a limited number of reports documenting rituximab's effectiveness, it should still be considered a viable treatment option for individuals with SPS who have not responded adequately to benzodiazepines and standard immunotherapies. [21]

Other Immunomodulatory Agents :

Corticosteroids have frequently been administered to patients with SPS, either alone or in combination with other treatments, leading to improvements in muscle spasms and reductions in autoantibody levels. However, high-quality clinical trials evaluating their overall effectiveness in SPS are lacking. Other immunomodulatory drugs, such as mycophenolate mofetil, azathioprine, cyclophosphamide, cyclosporine, tacrolimus, and sirolimus, have shown variable benefits in managing the condition. [16]

Non-Pharmacological:

A review of case reports has highlighted the symptomatic benefits of early physiotherapy. The physiotherapy treatments involved techniques such as relaxation, range of motion exercises, massage, ultrasound, heat therapy, hydrotherapy, and stretching. [22]

Psychotherapy can be beneficial for individuals with existing mental health issues as well as for children. [15]

Non-pharmacological approaches, including physical therapy, occupational therapy, aqua therapy, and acupuncture, can help alleviate muscle pain. Additionally, cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT) may assist patients in managing or avoiding emotional triggers that lead to muscle spasms, as well as in developing coping strategies for living with a chronic condition such as SPS. [23] [24]

Conclusion:

Stiff Person Syndrome is a rare neurological disorder with an autoimmune basis, requiring an integrated and multifaceted approach to treatment. While symptomatic treatments like benzodiazepines and baclofen provide relief from muscle rigidity and spasms, immunomodulatory therapies such as IVIG, corticosteroids, and rituximab target the underlying autoimmune process more directly. Emerging targeted treatments, including anti-cytokine therapies and B-cell-directed strategies, offer hope for patients with refractory or severe forms of the disease. A personalized, multidisciplinary approach combining pharmacologic, rehabilitative, and supportive care remains essential for optimal patient

outcomes. Continued research into disease mechanisms and treatment responses is crucial to improving long-term management and quality of life in SPS.

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